

Reference List for the Entry: IAT-Effekt [IAT effect]

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This document contains the full reference list from the encyclopedia entry “Röhner, J., & Schütz, A. (2021). IAT-Effekt. In M. Wirtz (Hrsg.), *Dorsch – Lexikon der Psychologie* (20. überarb. Aufl., S. 825). Hogrefe. . The original text is not included for copyright reasons. The reference list is provided here separately to help researchers find the cited works more easily.

References

1. Greenwald, A., Nosek, B. & Banaji, M. (2003). Understanding and using the Implicit Association Test: I. An improved scoring algorithm. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 85, 197-216. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.85.2.197>
2. Röhner, J. & Ewers, T. (2016). Trying to separate the wheat from the chaff: Construct- and faking-related variance on the Implicit Association Test (IAT). *Behavior Research Methods*, 48, 243-258. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-015-0568-1>